

The Number of Rooted Nearly 2-Regular Loopless Planar Maps

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Abstract: This paper investigates the enumeration of rooted nearly 2-regular loopless planar maps and presents some formulae for such maps with the valency of the root-face, the numbers of nonrooted vertices and inner faces as three parameters.

Key Words: Loopless map, nearly 2-regular map, enumerating function, functional equation, Lagrangian inversion.

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§1. Introduction

Since Tutte's papers on enumerating planar maps in [21–23] were published in the early 1960's, the enumerative theory has been developed greatly up to now. Eulerian maps have played a crucial role in enumerative map theory. In particular, Tutte's sum-free formula [22] for the number of eulerian planar maps, all of whose vertices are labelled and contain a distinguished edge-end, with a given sequence of (even) vertex valencies was an essential step in obtaining his ground-breaking formula for counting rooted planar maps by number of edges [23]. Several new results on the subject have been published since then (see, e.g. [1–20, 24]).

Here we deal with the enumeration of rooted nearly 2-regular loopless planar maps with the valency of the root-face, the numbers of nonrooted vertices and inner faces as three parameters. Several explicit expressions of its enumerating functions are obtained and one of them is summation-free.

A map is a connected graph cellularly embedded on a surface. A map is rooted if an edge and a direction along that edge are distinguished. If the root is the oriented edge from u to v , then u is the root-vertex while the face on the right side of the edge as seen by an observer on the edge facing away from u is defined as the root-face. A map is called Eulerian if all the valencies of its vertices are even. A nearly 2-regular map is a rooted map such that all vertices probably except the root-vertex are of valency 2. It is clear that a nearly 2-regular map is also an Eulerian map. In this paper, maps are always rooted and planar.

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For a set of some maps \mathcal{M} , the enumerating function discussed in this paper is defined as

$$f_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y, z) = \sum_{M \in \mathcal{M}} x^{l(M)} y^{p(M)} z^{q(M)}, \quad (1)$$

where $l(M)$, $p(M)$ and $q(M)$ are the root-face valency, the number of nonrooted vertices and the number of inner faces of M , respectively.

Furthermore, we introduce some other enumerating functions for \mathcal{M} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) &= \sum_{M \in \mathcal{M}} x^{l(M)} y^{n(M)}, \\ h_{\mathcal{M}}(y, z) &= \sum_{M \in \mathcal{M}} y^{p(M)} z^{q(M)}, \\ H_{\mathcal{M}}(y) &= \sum_{M \in \mathcal{M}} y^{n(M)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $l(M)$, $p(M)$ and $q(M)$ are the same in (1) and $n(M)$ is the number of edges of M , that is

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) &= f_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y, y), \quad h_{\mathcal{M}}(y, z) = f_{\mathcal{M}}(1, y, z), \\ H_{\mathcal{M}}(y) &= g_{\mathcal{M}}(1, y) = h_{\mathcal{M}}(y, y) = f_{\mathcal{M}}(1, y, y). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For the power series $f(x)$, $f(x, y)$ and $f(x, y, z)$, we employ the following notations:

$$\partial_x^l f(x), \quad \partial_{(x,y)}^{(l,p)} f(x, y) \quad \text{and} \quad \partial_{(x,y,z)}^{(l,p,q)} f(x, y, z)$$

to represent the coefficients of x^l in $f(x)$, $x^l y^p$ in $f(x, y)$ and $x^l y^p z^q$ in $f(x, y, z)$, respectively. Terminologies and notations not explained here can be found in [10].

§2. Functional Equations

In this section we will set up the functional equations satisfied by the enumerating functions for rooted nearly 2-regular loopless planar maps.

Let \mathcal{E} be the set of all rooted nearly 2-regular loopless planar maps with convention that the vertex map ϑ is in \mathcal{E} for convenience. For any $M \in \mathcal{E} - \vartheta$, it is obvious that each edge of M is contained in only one circuit. The circuit containing the root-edge is called the root circuit of M , and denoted by $C(M)$.

It is clear that the length of the root circuit is no more than the root-face valency, and

$$\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}_0 + \bigcup_{i \geq 2} \mathcal{E}_i, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathcal{E}_i = \{M \mid M \in \mathcal{E}, \text{ the length of } C(M) \text{ is } i\} \quad (5)$$

and \mathcal{E}_0 is only consist of the vertex map ϑ .

It is easy to see that the enumerating function of \mathcal{E}_0 is

$$f_{\mathcal{E}_0}(x, y, z) = 1. \quad (6)$$

For any $M \in \mathcal{E}_i$ ($i \geq 2$), the root circuit divides $M - C(M)$ into two domains, the inner domain and outer domain. The submap of M in the outer domain is a general map in \mathcal{E} , while the submap of M in the inner domain does not contribute the valency of the root-face of M . Thus, the enumerating function of \mathcal{E}_i is

$$f_{\mathcal{E}_i}(x, y, z) = x^i y^{i-1} z h f, \quad (7)$$

where $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z) = f_{\mathcal{E}}(1, y, z)$.

Theorem 2.1 *The enumerating function $f = f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z)$ satisfies the following equation:*

$$f = \left(1 - \frac{x^2 y z h}{1 - x y}\right)^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z) = f_{\mathcal{E}}(1, y, z)$.

Proof By (4), (6) and (7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} f &= 1 + \sum_{i \geq 2} x^i y^{i-1} z h f \\ &= 1 + \frac{x^2 y z h f}{1 - x y}, \end{aligned}$$

which is equivalent to the theorem. \square

Let $y = z$ in (8). Then we have

Corollary 2.1 *The enumerating function $g = g_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y)$ satisfies the following equation:*

$$g = \left(1 - \frac{x^2 y^2 H}{1 - x y}\right)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $H = H_{\mathcal{E}}(y) = g_{\mathcal{E}}(1, y)$.

Let $x = 1$ in (8). Then we obtain

Corollary 2.2 *The enumerating function $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z)$ satisfies the following equation:*

$$y z h^2 + (y - 1) h - y + 1 = 0. \quad (10)$$

Further, let $y = z$ in (10). Then we have

Corollary 2.3 *The enumerating function $H = H_{\mathcal{E}}(y)$ satisfies the following equation:*

$$y^2 H^2 + (y - 1)H - y + 1 = 0. \quad (11)$$

§3. Enumeration

In this section we will find the explicit formulae for enumerating functions $f = f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z)$, $g = g_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y)$, $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z)$ and $H = H_{\mathcal{E}}(y)$ by using Lagrangian inversion.

By (10) we have

$$h = \frac{(1 - y) \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4yz}{1 - y}} \right)}{2yz}. \quad (12)$$

Let

$$y = \frac{\theta}{1 + \theta}, \quad z = \eta(1 - \theta\eta). \quad (13)$$

By substituting (13) into (12), one may find that

$$h = \frac{1}{1 - \theta\eta}. \quad (14)$$

By (13) and (14), we have the following parametric expression of $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z)$:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \frac{\theta}{1 + \theta}, \quad z = \eta(1 - \theta\eta), \\ h &= \frac{1}{1 - \theta\eta} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and from which we get

$$\Delta_{(\theta, \eta)} = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{1 + \theta} & 0 \\ * & \frac{1 - 2\theta\eta}{1 - \theta\eta} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1 - 2\theta\eta}{(1 + \theta)(1 - \theta\eta)}. \quad (16)$$

Theorem 3.1 *The enumerating function $h = h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z)$ has the following explicit expression:*

$$h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z) = 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^p \frac{(2q)!(p-1)!}{q!(q+1)!(p-q)!(q-1)!} y^p z^q. \quad (17)$$

Proof By employing Lagrangian inversion with two parameters, from (15) and (16) one

may find that

$$\begin{aligned}
h_{\mathcal{E}}(y, z) &= \sum_{p, q \geq 0} \partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p, q)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-1} (1 - 2\theta\eta)}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+2}} y^p z^q \\
&= 1 + \sum_{p, q \geq 1} \left[\partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p, q)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-1}}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+2}} - 2\partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p-1, q-1)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-1}}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+2}} \right] y^p z^q \\
&= 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^p \frac{(2q)!}{q!(q+1)!} \partial_{\theta}^{p-q} (1 + \theta)^{p-1} y^p z^q = 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^p \frac{(2q)!(p-1)!}{q!(q+1)!(p-q)!(q-1)!} y^p z^q,
\end{aligned}$$

which is just the theorem. \square

In what follows we present a corollary of Theorem 3.1.

Corollary 3.1 *The enumerating function $H = H_{\mathcal{E}}(y)$ has the following explicit expression:*

$$H_{\mathcal{E}}(y) = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 2} \sum_{q=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(2q)!(n-q-1)!}{q!(q+1)!(n-2q)!(q-1)!} y^n. \quad (18)$$

Proof It follows immediately from (17) by putting $y = z$ and $n = p + q$. \square

Now, let

$$x = \frac{\xi(1 + \theta)}{1 + \xi\theta}. \quad (19)$$

By substituting (15) and (19) into Equ. (8), one may find that

$$f = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\xi^2 \theta \eta (1 + \theta)}{1 + \xi\theta}}. \quad (20)$$

By (15), (19) and (20), we have the parametric expression of the function $f = f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= \frac{\xi(1 + \theta)}{1 + \xi\theta}, & y &= \frac{\theta}{1 + \theta}, \\
z &= \eta(1 - \theta\eta), & f &= \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\xi^2 \theta \eta (1 + \theta)}{1 + \xi\theta}}.
\end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

According to (21), we have

$$\Delta_{(\xi, \theta, \eta)} = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{1 + \xi\theta} & * & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1 + \theta} & 0 \\ 0 & * & \frac{1 - 2\theta\eta}{1 - \theta\eta} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1 - 2\theta\eta}{(1 + \xi\theta)(1 + \theta)(1 - \theta\eta)}. \quad (22)$$

Theorem 3.2 *The enumerating function $f = f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z)$ has the following explicit expression:*

$$f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z) = 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^{p+q} \sum_{l=2}^{p+q} \sum_{k=\max\{1, \lceil \frac{l+q-p}{2} \rceil\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \frac{k}{q} \binom{2q-k-1}{q-k} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \\ \times \binom{p-l+k-1}{p-q-l+2k} x^l y^p z^q. \quad (23)$$

Proof By using Lagrangian inversion with three variables, from (21) and (22) one may find that

$$f_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y, z) = \sum_{l, p, q \geq 0} \partial_{(\xi, \theta, \eta)}^{(l, p, q)} \frac{(1 + \xi\theta)^{l-1} (1 + \theta)^{p-l-1} (1 - 2\theta\eta)}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+1} \left[1 - \frac{\xi^2 \theta \eta (1 + \theta)}{(1 + \xi\theta)} \right]} x^l y^p z^q \\ = \sum_{l, p, q \geq 0} \sum_{k=0}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, p, q\}} \partial_{(\xi, \theta, \eta)}^{(l-2k, p-k, q-k)} \frac{(1 + \xi\theta)^{l-k-1}}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+1}} \\ \times (1 + \theta)^{p-l+k-1} (1 - 2\theta\eta) x^l y^p z^q \\ = 1 + \sum_{p, q \geq 1} \sum_{l=2}^{p+q} \sum_{k=\max\{1, l-p\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \\ \times \partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p-l+k, q-k)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-l+k-1} (1 - 2\theta\eta)}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+1}} x^l y^p z^q \\ = 1 + \sum_{p, q \geq 1} \sum_{l=2}^{p+q} \sum_{k=\max\{1, l-p\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \\ \times \left[\partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p-l+k, q-k)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-l+k-1}}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+1}} \right. \\ \left. - 2 \partial_{(\theta, \eta)}^{(p-l+k-1, q-k-1)} \frac{(1 + \theta)^{p-l+k-1}}{(1 - \theta\eta)^{q+1}} \right] x^l y^p z^q \\ = 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^p \sum_{l=2}^{p+q} \sum_{k=\max\{1, \lceil \frac{l+q-p}{2} \rceil\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \frac{(2q-k-1)! k}{(q-k)! q!} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \\ \times \partial_{\theta}^{p-q-l+2k} (1 + \theta)^{p-l+k-1} x^l y^p z^q \\ = 1 + \sum_{p \geq 1} \sum_{q=1}^p \sum_{l=2}^{p+q} \sum_{k=\max\{1, \lceil \frac{l+q-p}{2} \rceil\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \frac{(2q-k-1)! k}{(q-k)! q!} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \\ \times \binom{p-l+k-1}{p-q-l+2k} x^l y^p z^q,$$

which is what we wanted. \square

Finally, we give a corollary of Theorem 3.2.

Corollary 3.2 *The enumerating function $g = g_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y)$ has the following explicit expression:*

$$g_{\mathcal{E}}(x, y) = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 2} \sum_{l=2}^n \sum_{q=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} \sum_{k=\max\{1, \lceil \frac{l+2q-n}{2} \rceil\}}^{\min\{\lfloor \frac{l}{2} \rfloor, q\}} \frac{k}{q} \binom{2q-k-1}{q-k} \binom{l-k-1}{l-2k} \times \binom{n-q-l+k-1}{n-2q-l+2k} x^l y^n. \quad (24)$$

Proof It follows soon from (23) by putting $y = z$ and $n = p + q$. \square

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